

Lifestyle Interventions and Physical Training in the Management of High Blood Pressure

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Abstract

The article presents a comprehensive characterization of hypertensive disease. Considerable attention is paid to the manifestations of essential arterial hypertension and symptomatic arterial hypertension [1,2]. Issues of non-pharmacological prevention of hypertensive disease are examined in detail, the basic principles of which should be followed by every patient [3]. A special place is devoted to highlighting the role of physical education and regular physical activity in the prevention of arterial hypertension and in slowing the progression of hypertensive disease [4,5]. The main principles of treatment of hypertensive disease are presented in detail, based on a rational combination of non-pharmacological interventions (lifestyle modification, physical education, dosed physical activity) and pharmacological antihypertensive therapy, as well as measures to prevent sharp increases in arterial blood pressure leading to severe complications [6].

Keywords: hypertensive disease, arterial hypertension, prevention of hypertensive disease, treatment of hypertensive disease, physical education.

Introduction

Hypertensive disease is among the most common diseases worldwide. This pathology is based on a persistent increase in vascular wall tone [1]. According to various epidemiological studies, the prevalence of hypertensive disease ranges from 20 to 33% of the global population [2].

Primary (true), or essential, hypertensive disease and symptomatic arterial hypertension are distinguished [1]. The development of essential hypertensive disease requires a prolonged period during which irreversible structural changes develop in the vascular wall. One of the key pathogenetic mechanisms is a pronounced decrease in vascular wall elasticity [3]. In this regard, the diagnosis of essential hypertensive disease is usually established in individuals over 45–50 years of age. At a young age, in the absence of early manifestations of atherosclerosis, formulation of this diagnosis is incorrect.

A number of congenital and acquired diseases of the central nervous system, cardiovascular system, and kidneys may manifest as symptomatic arterial hypertension [1,6]. These diseases are more often diagnosed at a young age. Surgical treatment of pathology of the brain, heart, kidneys, and their vessels in many cases makes it possible to eliminate the leading symptom—arterial hypertension [6].

The kidneys often manifest themselves as so-called “selfish organs,” primarily ensuring their own functioning. In the presence of obstacles to normal urine filtration, the renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system is activated, which leads to an increase in arterial blood pressure [6].

When extremely high values of arterial blood pressure are detected in a patient, pheochromocytoma—a benign tumor of the adrenal glands—must be excluded [1]. At the present stage, treatment of this disease is exclusively surgical.

Thus, essential hypertensive disease is predominantly characteristic of elderly individuals, whereas symptomatic arterial hypertension and various functional forms of arterial hypertension are more often observed in young patients. In cases of manifestation of arterial hypertension, its manifestations, as a rule, accompany the patient throughout life.

Prevention and treatment of arterial hypertension and hypertensive disease are possible using both non-pharmacological and pharmacological methods [3,4]. This work is of a review-analytical nature and is based on an analysis of scientific literature data, modern clinical guidelines, as well as many years of clinical and physical education observations by the author.

In modern clinical practice, prevention and treatment of arterial hypertension and hypertensive disease are considered as a single, multilevel process that includes non-pharmacological and pharmacological methods of intervention [3,4]. Non-pharmacological measures, primarily physical education and regular physical activity, are not opposed to drug therapy but act as its pathogenetic complement, making it possible to increase treatment effectiveness, stabilize blood pressure levels, and reduce the need for high doses of antihypertensive drugs.

The aim of this work is to analyze preventive methods that reduce the likelihood of developing arterial hypertension and hypertensive disease or significantly reduce the severity of their clinical manifestations, as well as to present the basic principles of treatment of these conditions.

Materials and Methods

The work summarizes the results of long-term observations of patients of various age groups, as well as students systematically engaged in physical education within the educational process and extracurricular physical culture and health-improving activities. The observations were longitudinal in nature and included assessment of clinical status, physical activity regimen, and lifestyle factors.

Blood pressure monitoring was carried out regularly and systematically: before physical activity, during its performance, and after completion of exercise sessions, as well as in everyday conditions [2]. Measurements were performed using standard sphygmomanometers in compliance with generally accepted methodological recommendations [2].

Statistical data processing was predominantly descriptive and included analysis of blood pressure dynamics, frequency of detection of borderline and pathological values, as well as assessment of trends in blood pressure changes against the background of non-pharmacological and pharmacological interventions.

Results and Discussion

Many outstanding physicians and cardiologists have addressed the problem of treating hypertensive disease and arterial hypertension; however, to date, methods for complete cure of essential hypertensive disease have not been developed [1].

One of the key aspects of managing patients with arterial hypertension and hypertensive disease is regular monitoring of blood pressure levels [2]. For this purpose, each patient is recommended to have an individual sphygmomanometer for self-measurement of blood pressure [2].

Healthcare professionals should consider the presence in some patients of the so-called “white coat” syndrome, caused by lability of the nervous system [1]. In such cases, blood pressure values measured in a medical setting exceed those recorded at home. This condition is often accompanied by tachycardia due to activation of the sympathetic nervous system [1].

Basal blood pressure level is distinguished—a parameter measured in bed immediately after awakening, in a state of complete rest. Working blood pressure is the level that predominates in a patient over a long period in the absence of clinical manifestations of hypertensive disease [2]. Blood pressure not exceeding 130/85 mmHg is considered normal, borderline values are up to 140/90 mmHg. Values exceeding these limits are classified as arterial hypertension [2].

In the clinical course of hypertensive disease, three stages are distinguished depending on the degree of target organ damage: Stage I—uncomplicated, Stage II—asymptomatic, Stage III—complicated [1]. According to the degree of blood pressure elevation, three degrees of hypertensive disease are distinguished: Grade I—mild, Grade II—moderate, Grade III—severe [1].

Hypertensive disease is characterized by a tendency toward gradual increase in blood pressure levels with an increase in numerical values over a certain period of time [6].

After the first recorded episode of persistent elevation of blood pressure, the patient is recommended to undergo inpatient examination with a full range of laboratory and instrumental studies [6]. The main objectives are to clarify the form of arterial hypertension, stabilize blood pressure levels, and individually select antihypertensive therapy [6]. After discharge from the hospital, the patient must be under dispensary supervision and undergo regular follow-up examinations [6].

In patients who suffered from arterial hypotension at a young age, the probability of developing hypertensive disease increases with age [1].

Normalization of work and rest regimen, ensuring adequate eight-hour sleep, and minimizing exposure to stress factors are of great importance [3].

Attention should be paid to rational and balanced nutrition. In cases of elevated cholesterol levels, a hypocholesterolemic diet is recommended. Atherosclerosis and hypertensive disease often coexist, mutually enhancing their adverse effects on the body [1].

Physical education and regular dosed physical activity are of substantial importance in the prevention and treatment of arterial hypertension, as well as in slowing the progression of

hypertensive disease [4,5]. Systematic physical loads contribute to improved regulation of vascular tone, reduction of blood cholesterol and glucose levels, decrease in fluid retention in tissues, and normalization of hormonal balance [4,5].

At all stages of hypertensive disease, moderate physical loads are indicated: walking, skiing, cycling until the first signs of fatigue appear, and work on personal household plots [4].

A special place is occupied by organized physical education classes, including elements of gymnastics, swimming, active and sports-and-health games, as well as general physical training [5].

Long-term observations of students regularly engaged in physical education at the Department of Physical Education of NTU “KhPI” showed that in some cases manifestations of borderline arterial hypertension, neurocirculatory dystonia, and symptomatic hypertension were observed [4].

Participation in physical culture and health programs of NTU “KhPI” includes not only students but also representatives of children’s, youth, and veteran groups, which expands the possibilities for prevention of cardiovascular diseases across different age categories [4,5].

Systematic physical training, normalization of nutrition and sleep regimen, and reduction of stress load in most cases led to normalization of blood pressure indicators [4].

Essential hypertensive disease, considering the peculiarities of its pathogenesis, is practically not encountered at a young age, whereas in young individuals engaged in physical education, various forms of arterial hypertension of functional or symptomatic nature are more often registered [4].

Regular physical education contributes to the formation of stable skills for body weight control and metabolic processes, exerting a preventive effect on the development of metabolic syndrome and disorders of vascular tone [5].

Physical culture activities are accompanied by moderate emotional reactions and activation of neurohumoral mechanisms, including the production of adrenaline, endorphins, dopamine, serotonin, and endocannabinoids [4]. The influence of these mediators on the vascular wall contributes to optimal regulation of vascular tone and maintenance of the morphofunctional state of the cardiovascular system [4].

The formation of high quality of life largely occurs at a young age. The intensity of physical education in the presence of arterial hypertension is determined by the stage of the disease, the level of working blood pressure, and the volume of pharmacological therapy in concomitant hypertensive disease [3,5].

In most cases, regular physical training contributes to a decrease in blood pressure levels in individuals with arterial hypertension and is an important component of complex therapy in patients with hypertensive disease receiving pharmacological treatment [3,5]. Against the background of systematic dosed physical activity, an increase in sensitivity to antihypertensive

drugs is often observed, which makes it possible to reduce their daily doses without loss of control over blood pressure levels.

Blood pressure monitoring is especially necessary for individuals with arterial hypertension, as well as patients diagnosed with hypertensive disease, before, during, and after physical exertion [2,5]. At blood pressure values of 160/100 mmHg and higher in individuals with arterial hypertension or hypertensive disease, physical loads should be canceled [2]. After a hypertensive crisis, active physical activities are possible no earlier than two weeks after complete relief of symptoms [2].

Conducting physical education and therapeutic physical activity in patients receiving antihypertensive therapy requires consideration of the pharmacodynamic effects of medications. Beta-blockers, calcium antagonists, and diuretics may alter exercise tolerance, heart rate, and vascular tone response, which necessitates individual selection of the volume and intensity of physical training [5,6]. Thus, physical education in hypertensive disease should be regarded as an element of a comprehensive therapeutic process implemented in close connection with pharmacological therapy.

Pharmacological Treatment of Hypertensive Disease

Pharmacological treatment of hypertensive disease is not an isolated method of intervention and is most effective when combined with non-pharmacological measures, including lifestyle modification and regular physical activity [3,6]. The prescription of antihypertensive drugs creates a hemodynamic basis against which dosed physical loads can realize their preventive and rehabilitative effects without the risk of complications.

There are many classes of drugs that lower blood pressure. Their diversity reflects the active search by pharmaceutical companies for effective treatment methods and confirms that therapy for hypertensive disease has not yet been fully developed [6].

In recent years, a number of long-acting drugs have been created, a single dose of which allows maintenance of normal blood pressure levels for up to 24 hours, that is, such drugs are taken once daily [6].

To achieve optimal therapeutic effect, combination therapy using several drugs from different groups is often employed. For example, a combination of a beta-blocker, a slow calcium channel blocker, an angiotensin II receptor antagonist, and a potassium-sparing diuretic is possible.

When using angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, approximately 20% of patients may develop a dry, irritating cough without fever. In this case, the drug should be discontinued and replaced with agents from another pharmacological group.

Slow calcium channel blockers with predominant vascular effects may cause limb edema; therefore, their use is recommended only in combination with potassium-sparing diuretics.

Some beta-blockers and slow calcium channel blockers may increase blood glucose levels, which requires monitoring of metabolic parameters in patients with hypertensive disease [6].

A patient with hypertensive disease should monitor blood pressure at least twice daily, preferably in the morning and evening, using a sphygmomanometer. Depending on the obtained values, doses of antihypertensive drugs are adjusted. At moderate blood pressure values, the dose may be reduced; at high values, increased. In the case of normal pressure, a single omission of the drug dose is possible; this regimen is referred to as “on demand”.

There is also systematic daily intake of a maintenance dose of antihypertensive agents. The goal of such therapy is to prevent sharp surges in blood pressure that can lead to severe complications: rupture of the vascular wall, hypertensive encephalopathy, hypertensive crisis, myocardial infarction, or stroke.

A feature of hypertensive disease is its asymptomatic onset: in the early stages of pressure elevation, the patient’s general well-being may remain satisfactory, with no pain or discomfort. When clinical symptoms manifest, inpatient treatment, injections, or intravenous administration of drugs may be required to normalize the condition. Therefore, prevention and regular blood pressure monitoring are extremely important [6].

After taking antihypertensive drugs, hypotension may occur. In this case, vascular tone decreases, weakness, sweating, dizziness, and other symptoms appear. Such a reaction is usually associated with exceeding the individual drug dose. The patient should be placed in a horizontal position with elevated legs, take strong tea or coffee, and carefully monitor blood pressure dynamics. If no improvement occurs, emergency medical assistance is required to correct vascular tone [6].

Conclusion

Strict adherence to preventive measures, systematic blood pressure monitoring, regular physical education in combination with rationally selected pharmacological therapy, according to modern clinical guidelines, make it possible to maintain stable blood pressure indicators and satisfactory quality of life in patients with arterial hypertension and hypertensive disease for a long time [1–6]. Physical education in this context is not an alternative to drug treatment but its obligatory functional complement, ensuring long-term stabilization of vascular tone and reduction of the risk of cardiovascular complications.

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